

A closer look at Doleac and Mukherjee (2022) and the effects of naloxone access laws on opioid ER admissions

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Doleac and Mukherjee (2022) conclude that broadening access to a life-saving drug — naloxone — does not reduce opioid-related mortality as the drug simultaneously encourages riskier drug use. I show issues with their data, design, and estimation methods. For example, their Google Search data has an unverifiable origin, the law timing is incorrect, and the statistical inference is invalid. Correcting these issues within a triple difference design shows that naloxone, contrary to their findings, does not increase ER opioid admissions. I conclude that the moral hazard (and the ensuing adverse consequences) of naloxone use lacks empirical support.

1. Introduction

Drugs overdose is a global concern with profound implications. In 2023, nearly 107,000 deaths in the United States alone were attributed to drug overdoses, marking a 55% increase from the 72,000 deaths recorded in 2020. Approximately 80% of these deaths are linked to opioids, encompassing both prescription painkillers like oxycodone and illicit drugs such as heroin and fentanyl (NVSS, 2023).

Opioid overdose results from excessive depression of the respiratory and central nervous systems. Naloxone, an opioid receptor competitive antagonist, counteracts this effect by displacing opioids from these receptors (Chamberlain and Klein 1994). At least 40% of overdose victims are not alone when they overdose (Mattson et al. 2018). Administering naloxone to these individuals by bystanders could prevent most witnessed deaths and potentially save lives, even in cases where help arrives after the overdose.

Despite its life-saving potential, naloxone is often not readily available when needed most. While certain formulations require a prescription, naloxone is not a controlled substance and carries no risk of abuse. Traditionally used by first responders, naloxone can also be easily administered by laypeople with minimal training (Wheeler et al. 2015). Recognizing its importance, all 50 states and the District of Columbia had enacted legislation to enhance layperson naloxone access by July 15, 2017 (Davis and Carr 2015).

Using staggered timing of state-level naloxone access laws and a difference-in-difference (DD) design, Doleac and Mukherjee (2022) (henceforth DM) employ spatial-level data of various granularities to analyze the impact of these laws. They begin with Google Trends data, which shows a decrease in searches for drug treatment alongside an increase in searches for naloxone. Then, they find an increase in drug-related crime, as evidenced by data from the National Incident-Based Reporting System (NIBRS). The analysis further

Significance Statement

Drug policies are uniquely sensitive to public opinion, underscoring the pressing need for quality and responsible research. Doleac and Mukherjee (2022) conclude that laws designed to increase access to Narcan do not reduce mortality and instead increase opioid use intensity. Despite contradicting studies published both before and after, their paper has received widespread publicity in the media and policy think tanks. This work reveals unreproducible results. Corrections show no effect on opioid use intensity as proxied by ER admissions.

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reveals an increase in emergency room (ER) visits, utilizing data from the Healthcare Cost and Utilization Project (HCUP), while mortality data from restricted-use Linked Mortality Files (LMFs) show no change. DM interpret these empirical findings as evidence that naloxone makes opioid use safer, leading to riskier drug use, ultimately resulting in a net effect of zero on mortality. They draw a theoretical parallel with the impact of seat belts or automobile insurance on risky driving, suggesting that such interventions may inadvertently encourage riskier behavior through the mechanism of moral hazard.

The study by DM has garnered significant media attention, featuring prominently in outlets such as The Atlantic, Washington Post, The Times, Globe and Mail, Forbes, Buzzfeed, Wall Street Journal, CNN, and The Economist, with extensively favorable reporting. The authors also promoted their results via The Brookings Institution, an influential think tank at the forefront of public policy (Doleac, Mukherjee, and Schnell 2018).

However, the conclusions of their study stand in contradiction to a wealth of evidence accumulated over decades by clinicians and medical researchers (e.g., Tse et al. 2022; McDonald and Strang 2016), as well as economists (Rees et al. 2019). This contradiction is particularly notable because DM’s research employs data and methods similar to those of other researchers. Subsequent papers utilizing similar data on mortality have also demonstrated various benefits of naloxone in terms of reducing opioid-related deaths (e.g., Tabatabai et al. 2023).

The current study attempts to replicate the DM results using the statistical program that underpins their conclusions, which is available as supplemental material to their paper and can be publicly downloaded. While most datasets used in the analysis are available for reanalysis and scrutiny, LMFs are not included in the replication package. My work adheres to the principles of policing replication explained in Ankel-Peters, Fiala, and Neubauer (2023), which involves directly engaging with the original work in the title or abstract. For this paper, I apply the replication taxonomy proposed by Dreber and Johannesson (2024), endorsed by the Institute for Replication (I4R, 2024).

Section 2 begins with the narrowest definition of replication: computational reproducibility. This entails running the code submitted by the authors and comparing the results with those reported in the paper. The limitation of this approach is that even if the results reproduce computationally, they still could be flawed due to errors in cleaning the raw data. Therefore, Section 3 transitions to another form of reproducibility: recreate reproducibility. This involves exploring the feasibility of accessing the original raw data without relying on the DM package. Subsequently, I test or compare the independently retrieved data and the data contained within the package. I address robustness reproducibility in the subsequent Section 4. Here, I discuss DM’s estimation design and demonstrate the non-robustness of their conclusions if their design on their data is implemented using more plausible data modeling assumptions. Section 5 demonstrates my own empirical results, correcting the issues discussed in the previous sections.

2. Reported results

Table 1 reports the output of the DM replication package and the results reported in the published manuscript. The results that replicate exactly are omitted from the table. The discrepancies are present and also discernible without accessing and executing the replication package, as the reported standard errors do not match the indicated confidence interval. There should be three stars for the outcome ‘Possession of Opioids’ since the reported errors imply t -statistic of 5.98. Similar reporting issues are evident in the working paper (Doleac and Mukherjee 2018), suggesting that the errors did not result from copy editing or typesetting. Likewise, the outcome ‘Opioid-related ER visits’ should be significant at five percent as shown in the replication package, but DM reports it to be significant at ten percent. The overall conclusion is that the computational reproducibility of the DM results has failed in the exact sense.

Table 1. Computational reproducibility

	Replication package			Reported in DM	
	Estimate	SE	P value	Estimate	SE
Google search naloxone	1.847*	0.813	0.028	1.847*	0.809
Google search drug rehab	-0.799+	0.453	0.084	-0.799+	0.450
Opioid-related ER visits	265.909*	121.691	0.037	265.9+	121.6
Possession of opioids	4.030*	1.674	0.023	4.030*	0.675
Selling opioids	1.917**	0.675	0.008	1.917**	0.214

+ $p < 0.1$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Notes: The right column copies coefficients from DM; the left column shows results from their replication package.

Source: DM (2022) replication package (all data files).

It is also of minor note that the final sentence in the notes beneath Table 3 of DM that reports the main results contains a mistake. The note states that, ‘Coefficients in the first four columns are population weighted, as the dependent variable is a rate.’ It arguably should read ‘the last four columns’ instead, as this is where rates are reported. Rates also do not justify weights, as discussed in Solon, Haider, and Wooldridge (2015) and confirmed by Gary Solon in the review of this replication. In addition, the population does not vary in the regressions conditional on state fixed effects (if the population is included in the model, Stata drops it due to collinearity). Their replication code also shows they use analytic weights, not population.

3. Data

A. Google search. As explained in DM, two outcomes are based on monthly metropolitan-level Google searches covering the period of 2010-2015. This is the key outcome that underpins their moral hazard narrative that links crime and hospitalization findings. They argue that an increase in Google searches for naloxone indicates that legal access to the drug led to broad interest in obtaining it, while a decrease in drug rehabilitation searches indicates a lack of interest in opioid treatment. I report on the search item related to naloxone, but everything discussed applies to the search item related to drug rehabilitation as well.

In line with DM’s methodology, we focus on search terms ‘naloxone,’ ‘narcan,’ and related queries. Using Google Trends for the first month of their study period: 2010m1, we identified ‘narcan medication’ as an additional term suggested by Google. This data can be accessed via the Google Trends web interface, with results available through a permanent link (Google Trends 2023). Google Trends does not use the entire universe of searches in its analysis. Instead, it relies on a random sample of searches to generate its results. This sampling method causes data variations, making independent retrieval of the same data impossible. However, the data that can be retrieved is structurally different from what is in the DM package. While there is an alternative method of accessing Google Trends data through its Application Programming Interface (API), this method does not provide improved data granularity. The API offers the same level of detail as the web interface, merely providing an automated means of data retrieval.

It can be verified that the web results for this request show sparse time series data with only a few dates showing nonzero values. The metropolitan area heat map is primarily grey, indicating that data for most metropolitan areas in a cross-sectional data for 2010m1 does not exist. Table 2 shows the metropolitan-level data that can be exported and used in the analysis. This is the data presumably used in DM. In the table, out of 210 metropolitan areas, only 22 have a value, and none have zeros. To make better sense of this table, I will now consult the manual by Stephens-Davidowitz and Varian (2015), which provides guidance on how to use Google Trends in research.

The manual provides critical details that DM assume the reader already knows, as they omit the discussion on the nature and limitations of the Google Trends output. The table shows the number of sought-after search items relative to all Google searches. This is a convenient quantity for the analysis, as it implicitly controls for location- and time- specific numbers of active internet users. Out of privacy concerns, the actual ratios are not shown; instead, they are normalized so that the highest-scoring location has 100.

The cells with missing data (most of the set) result from an additional privacy threshold. If total searches are below that threshold, a ‘.’ is reported. This means that not enough requests were made to advance past the threshold. The privacy threshold is based on the absolute number of Google searches. For example, DM say that they search for ‘naloxone (drug),’ but this search result is extremely rare. It only shows once in the state of Florida, with the related query being completely empty (not enough data).

Data that is too frequent (monthly, in our case) and places that are too small (metropolitan areas) have more missing values. To address this issue, Stephens-Davidowitz and Varian (2015) suggest using a coarser time period or geography — for instance, Stephens-Davidowitz (2014) pools three years of data to the state level. Even then, as Appendix C explains, he employs an elaborate strategy to handle the privacy threshold. He adds extraneous search items and then uses ordinary least squares (OLS) and two-stage least squares estimates to clean them from the ultimate sample. These challenges suggest that complete monthly metropolitan-level data, as used in DM’s analysis, may be difficult to fully obtain. This raises the question: what data is actually included in the replication package?

Table 2. Counterexample Google Trends data for 2010m1

N	Metro	IDX	N	Metro	IDX	N	Metro	IDX
1	Bluefield-Beckley-Oak Hill WV	100	71	Rochester NY	141	141	San Angelo TX	.
2	Clarksburg-Weston WV	75	72	Tampa-St. Petersburg (Sarasota) FL	142	142	Abilene-Sweetwater TX	.
3	Terre Haute IN	44	73	Traverse City-Cadillac MI	143	143	Madison WI	.
4	Biloxi-Gulfport MS	42	74	Lexington KY	144	144	Ft. Smith-Fayetteville-Springdale-Rogers AR	.
5	Monroe LA-El Dorado AR	37	75	Dayton OH	145	145	Tulsa OK	.
6	Joplin MO-Pittsburg KS	32	76	Springfield-Holyoke MA	146	146	Columbus-Tupelo-West Point MS	.
7	Salisbury MD	32	77	Norfolk-Portsmouth-Newport News VA	147	147	Peoria-Bloomington IL	.
8	Augusta GA	26	78	Greenville-New Bern-Washington NC	148	148	Duluth MN-Superior WI	.
9	Beaumont-Port Arthur TX	23	79	Columbia SC	149	149	Wichita-Hutchinson KS	.
10	Macon GA	13	80	Toledo OH	150	150	Des Moines-Ames IA	.
11	Chattanooga TN	10	81	West Palm Beach-Ft. Pierce FL	151	151	Davenport IA-Rock Island-Moline IL	.
12	Rochester MN-Mason City IA-Austin MN	10	82	Watertown NY	152	152	Mobile AL-Pensacola (Ft. Walton Beach) FL	.
13	Lafayette LA	10	83	Wilmington NC	153	153	Minot-Bismarck-Dickinson(Williston) ND	.
14	Champaign & Springfield-Decatur IL	9	84	Lansing MI	154	154	Huntsville-Decatur (Florence) AL	.
15	La Crosse-Eau Claire WI	8	85	Marquette MI	155	155	Little Rock-Pine Bluff AR	.
16	Tri-Cities TN-VA	8	86	Wheeling WV-Steubenville OH	156	156	Montgomery (Selma) AL	.
17	Waco-Temple-Bryan TX	8	87	Syracuse NY	157	157	Wausau-Rhineland WI	.
18	Charleston-Huntington WV	7	88	Knoxville TN	158	158	Tyler-Longview(Lufkin & Nacogdoches) TX	.
19	Fresno-Visalia CA	7	89	Lima OH	159	159	Hattiesburg-Laurel MS	.
20	Anchorage AK	7	90	Jacksonville FL	160	160	Meridian MS	.
21	South Bend-Elkhart IN	7	91	Grand Rapids-Kalamazoo-Battle Creek MI	161	161	Baton Rouge LA	.
22	Lincoln & Hastings-Kearney NE	6	92	Elmira NY	162	162	Quincy IL-Hannibal MO-Keokuk IA	.
23	Richmond-Petersburg VA	5	93	Harrisburg-Lancaster-Lebanon-York PA	163	163	Jackson MS	.
24	Cincinnati OH	2	94	Greenville-Spartanburg SC-Asheville NC-Anderson SC	164	164	Fargo-Valley City ND	.
25	Raleigh-Durham (Fayetteville) NC	2	95	Harrisonburg VA	165	165	Sioux Falls(Mitchell) SD	.
26	San Antonio TX	2	96	Florence-Myrtle Beach SC	166	166	Jonesboro AR	.
27	Detroit MI	2	97	Ft. Myers-Naples FL	167	167	Bowling Green KY	.
28	Houston TX	1	98	Roanoke-Lynchburg VA	168	168	Mankato MN	.
29	Baltimore MD	1	99	Johnstown-Altoona PA	169	169	North Platte NE	.
30	Philadelphia PA	1	100	Wilkes Barre-Scranton PA	170	170	Honolulu HI	.
31	Minneapolis-St. Paul MN	1	101	Lafayette IN	171	171	Fairbanks AK	.
32	Miami-Ft. Lauderdale FL	1	102	Alpena MI	172	172	Juneau AK	.
33	Phoenix AZ	1	103	Charlottesville VA	173	173	Laredo TX	.
34	Denver CO	1	104	Gainesville FL	174	174	Colorado Springs-Pueblo CO	.
35	New York NY	<1	105	Zanesville OH	175	175	Butte-Bozeman MT	.
36	Boston MA-Manchester NH	<1	106	Corpus Christi TX	176	176	Great Falls MT	.
37	Atlanta GA	<1	107	Chicago IL	177	177	Billings, MT	.
38	Los Angeles CA	<1	108	Columbia-Jefferson City MO	178	178	Boise ID	.
39	Washington DC (Hagerstown MD)	<1	109	Topeka KS	179	179	Idaho Falls-Pocatello ID	.
40	Parkersburg WV	110	110	Dothan AL	180	180	Cheyenne WY-Scottsbluff NE	.
41	Presque Isle ME	111	111	St. Louis MO	181	181	Twin Falls ID	.
42	Greenwood-Greenville MS	112	112	Rockford IL	182	182	Missoula MT	.
43	Victoria TX	113	113	Shreveport LA	183	183	Rapid City SD	.
44	Lake Charles LA	114	114	Kansas City MO	184	184	El Paso TX	.
45	Portland-Auburn ME	115	115	Milwaukee WI	185	185	Helena MT	.
46	Binghamton NY	116	116	Springfield MO	186	186	Casper-Riverton WY	.
47	Savannah GA	117	117	New Orleans LA	187	187	Salt Lake City UT	.
48	Pittsburgh PA	118	118	Dallas-Ft. Worth TX	188	188	Yuma AZ-El Centro CA	.
49	Ft. Wayne IN	119	119	Sioux City IA	189	189	Grand Junction-Montrose CO	.
50	Cleveland-Akron (Canton) OH	120	120	Wichita Falls TX & Lawton OK	190	190	Tucson (Sierra Vista) AZ	.
51	Flint-Saginaw-Bay City MI	121	121	Birmingham AL	191	191	Albuquerque-Santa Fe NM	.
52	Buffalo NY	122	122	Ottumwa IA-Kirkville MO	192	192	Glendive MT	.
53	Erie PA	123	123	Paducah KY-Cape Girardeau MO-Harrisburg-Mount Vernon IL	193	193	Bakersfield CA	.
54	Charlotte NC	124	124	Odessa-Midland TX	194	194	Eugene OR	.
55	Greensboro-High Point-Winston Salem NC	125	125	Amarillo TX	195	195	Eureka CA	.
56	Charleston SC	126	126	Austin TX	196	196	Palm Springs CA	.
57	Providence RI-New Bedford MA	127	127	Harlingen-Weslaco-Brownsville-McAllen TX	197	197	San Francisco-Oakland-San Jose CA	.
58	Columbus GA	128	128	Cedar Rapids-Waterloo-Iowa City & Dubuque IA	198	198	Yakima-Pasco-Richland-Kennewick WA	.
59	Burlington VT-Plattsburgh NY	129	129	St. Joseph MO	199	199	Reno NV	.
60	Albany NY	130	130	Jackson TN	200	200	Medford-Klamath Falls OR	.
61	Utica NY	131	131	Memphis TN	201	201	Seattle-Tacoma WA	.
62	Indianapolis IN	132	132	Alexandria LA	202	202	Portland OR	.
63	Louisville KY	133	133	Evansville IN	203	203	Bend OR	.
64	Tallahassee FL-Thomasville GA	134	134	Oklahoma City OK	204	204	San Diego CA	.
65	Albany-Schenectady-Troy NY	135	135	Lubbock TX	205	205	Monterey-Salinas CA	.
66	Hartford & New Haven CT	136	136	Omaha NE	206	206	Las Vegas NV	.
67	Orlando-Daytona Beach-Melbourne FL	137	137	Panama City FL	207	207	Santa Barbara-Santa Maria-San Luis Obispo CA	.
68	Columbus OH	138	138	Sherman TX-Ada OK	208	208	Sacramento-Stockton-Modesto CA	.
69	Youngstown OH	139	139	Green Bay-Appleton WI	209	209	Chico-Redding CA	.
70	Bangor ME	140	140	Nashville TN	210	210	Spokane WA	.

Notes: Search results for naloxone and related queries for 2010m1.
 Source: Google Trends (2023).

Table 3. DM's Google Trends data for 2010m1

N	Metro	IDX	N	Metro	IDX	N	Metro	IDX	N	Metro	IDX
1	ShermanTXAdaOK1	100	76	SpringfieldHolyokeM1	37	151	SiouxCityIA1	0	226	FargoValleyCityND1	0
2	ShermanTXAdaOK1	100	77	RoanokeLynchburgVA1	37	152	SavannahGA1	0	227	EvansvilleIN1	0
3	SaltLakeCityUT1	100	78	PhiladelphiaPA1	37	153	SavannahGA1	0	228	EurekaCA1	0
4	SaltLakeCityUT1	100	79	NewYorkNY1	37	154	SantaBarbaraSantaMar	0	229	EugeneOR1	0
5	RichmondPetersburgV1	100	80	NewYorkNY1	37	155	SalisburyMD1	0	230	EriePA1	0
6	HarrisonburgVA1	100	81	ChattanoogaTN1	37	156	SalisburyMD1	0	231	ElmiraNY1	0
7	HarrisonburgVA1	100	82	StLouisMO1	34	157	RockfordIL1	0	232	ElmiraNY1	0
8	HarlingenWeslacoBrow	100	83	WestPalmBeachFtPierc	33	158	RochesterMNMasonCity	0	233	ElPasoTX1	0
9	GreenBayAppletonWI1	100	84	SanFranciscoOaklandS	33	159	RochesterMNMasonCity	0	234	ElPasoTX1	0
10	WichitaFallsTXLawton	96	85	PittsburghPA1	32	160	RenoNV1	0	235	DuluthMNSuperiorWI1	0
11	WichitaFallsTXLawton	96	86	BatonRougeLA1	32	161	RenoNV1	0	236	DothanAL1	0
12	DesMoinesAmesIA1	96	87	PhiladelphiaPA1	31	162	RapidCitySD1	0	237	DothanAL1	0
13	ChattanoogaTN1	90	88	MinneapolisStPaulMN1	30	163	RapidCitySD1	0	238	DavenportIARockIslan	0
14	CharlestonSC1	87	89	HartfordNewHavenCT1	30	164	QuincyLHannibalMOke	0	239	DavenportIARockIslan	0
15	WichitaHutchinsonKS1	85	90	BurlingtonVTPlattsbu	30	165	QuincyLHannibalMOke	0	240	CorpusChristiTX1	0
16	IdahoFallsPocatellol	83	91	BurlingtonVTPlattsbu	30	166	PortlandAuburnME1	0	241	ColumbusTupeloWestPo	0
17	FtSmithFayettevilleS	81	92	BurlingtonVTPlattsbu	30	167	PortlandAuburnME1	0	242	ColumbusGA1	0
18	ChampaignSpringfield	81	93	TampaStPetersburgSar	29	168	PeoriaBloomingtonIL1	0	243	ColumbusGA1	0
19	SeattleTacomaWA1	75	94	DetroitMI1	28	169	ParkersburgWV1	0	244	ColumbiaJeffersonCit	0
20	CharlotteNC1	75	95	DenverCO1	28	170	ParkersburgWV1	0	245	ColoradoSpringsPuebl	0
21	FresnoVisaliaCA1	74	96	NashvilleTN1	27	171	PanamaCityFL1	0	246	ClarksburgWestonWV1	0
22	PortlandOR1	68	97	MiamiFtLauderdaleFL1	27	172	PalmSpringsCA1	0	247	ChicoReddingCA1	0
23	HarrisburgLancasterL	66	98	RaleighDurhamFayette	26	173	PaducahKYCapeGirarde	0	248	CheyenneWYScottsbluf	0
24	PortlandOR1	64	99	OrlandoDaytonaBeachM	26	174	PaducahKYCapeGirarde	0	249	CheyenneWYScottsbluf	0
25	MobileALPensacolaFW	63	100	MinneapolisStPaulMN1	26	175	PaducahKYCapeGirarde	0	250	CharlottesvilleVA1	0
26	MobileALPensacolaFW	63	101	DenverCO1	26	176	OklahomaCityOK1	0	251	CharlotteNC1	0
27	PhoenixAZ1	62	102	ProvidenceRINewBedfo	25	177	OdessaMidlandTX1	0	252	CharlestonHuntington	0
28	JacksonvilleFL1	62	103	PhiladelphiaPA1	25	178	NorfolkPortsmouthNew	0	253	CharlestonHuntington	0
29	JacksonvilleFL1	62	104	DallasFtWorthTX1	25	179	NorfolkPortsmouthNew	0	254	CharlestonHuntington	0
30	KansasCityMO1	61	105	BuffaloNY1	25	180	NewOrleansLA1	0	255	CedarRapidsWaterloo	0
31	MemphisTN1	59	106	BuffaloNY1	25	181	NashvilleTN1	0	256	ButteBozemanMT1	0
32	MemphisTN1	59	107	CincinnatiOH1	22	182	MontereySalinasCA1	0	257	BowlingGreenKY1	0
33	LouisvilleKY1	57	108	BaltimoreMD1	22	183	MonroeLAElDoradoAR1	0	258	BoiseID1	0
34	LouisvilleKY1	57	109	KansasCityMO1	20	184	MonroeLAElDoradoAR1	0	259	BoiseID1	0
35	HonoluluHI1	57	110	DenverCO1	19	185	MissoulaMT1	0	260	BluefieldBeckleyOakH	0
36	EvansvilleIN1	55	111	WashingtonDCHagersto	17	186	MinotBismarckDickins	0	261	BluefieldBeckleyOakH	0
37	EvansvilleIN1	55	112	WashingtonDCHagersto	17	187	MinotBismarckDickins	0	262	BinghamtonNY1	0
38	AustinTX1	55	113	WashingtonDCHagersto	17	188	MilwaukeeWI1	0	263	BiloxiGulfportMS1	0
39	WausauRhinelanderWI1	54	114	ChicagoIL1	12	189	MemphisTN1	0	264	BillingsMT1	0
40	OmahaNE1	52	115	ChicagoIL1	9	190	MedfordKlamathFallsO	0	265	BillingsMT1	0
41	DuluthMNSuperiorWI1	52	116	BostonMAManchesterN1	7	191	MedfordKlamathFallsO	0	266	BendOR1	0
42	ColumbusOH1	52	117	BostonMAManchesterN1	7	192	MaconGA1	0	267	BeaumontPortArthurT1	0
43	MontgomerySelmaAL1	51	118	ZanesvilleOH1	0	193	LubbockTX1	0	268	BatonRougeLA1	0
44	ColumbiaSC1	51	119	YumaAZEICentroCA1	0	194	LittleRockPineBluffA	0	269	BangorME1	0
45	CincinnatiOH1	51	120	YumaAZEICentroCA1	0	195	LincolnHastingsKearn	0	270	BakersfieldCA1	0
46	CincinnatiOH1	51	121	YoungstownOH1	0	196	LimaOH1	0	271	AugustaGA1	0
47	SouthBendElkhartIN1	50	122	YoungstownOH1	0	197	LexingtonKY1	0	272	AugustaGA1	0
48	SanAntonioTX1	50	123	YakimaPascoRichlandK	0	198	LasVegasNV1	0	273	AnchorageAK1	0
49	SacramentoStocktonMo	50	124	YakimaPascoRichlandK	0	199	LaredoTX1	0	274	AmarilloTX1	0
50	ToledoOH1	49	125	WilmingtonNC1	0	200	LansingMI1	0	275	AmarilloTX1	0
51	ToledoOH1	49	126	WilkesBarreScrantonP	0	201	LakeCharlesLA1	0	276	AmarilloTX1	0
52	KnoxvilleTN1	49	127	WheelingWVSteubenvil	0	202	LafayetteLA1	0	277	AlexandriaLA1	0
53	KnoxvilleTN1	48	128	WheelingWVSteubenvil	0	203	LafayetteLA1	0	278	AlbuquerqueSantaFeN1	0
54	IndianapolisIN1	48	129	WatertownNY1	0	204	LaCrosseEauClaireWI1	0	279	AlbanyScheneectadyTio	0
55	FlintSaginawBayCityM	48	130	WacoTempleBryanTX1	0	205	LaCrosseEauClaireWI1	0	280	AlbanyGA1	0
56	StLouisMO1	47	131	UticaNY1	0	206	JoplinMOPittsburgKS1	0	281	AbileneSweetwaterTX1	0
57	ShreveportLA1	47	132	TylerLongviewLufkinN	0	207	JoplinMOPittsburgKS1	0	282	VictoriaTX1	.
58	ShreveportLA1	47	133	TulsaOK1	0	208	JonesboroAR1	0	283	TwinFallsID1	.
59	OmahaNE1	47	134	TucsonSierraVistaAZ1	0	209	JohnstownAltoonaPA1	0	284	StJosephMO1	.
60	GainesvilleFL1	47	135	TriCitiesTNVA1	0	210	JacksonTN1	0	285	StJosephMO1	.
61	BirminghamAL1	47	136	TriCitiesTNVA1	0	211	IdahoFallsPocatellol	0	286	SanAngeloTX1	.
62	SouthBendElkhartIN1	45	137	TriCitiesTNVA1	0	212	HuntsvilleDecaturFlo	0	287	PresqueIsleME1	.
63	ShreveportLA1	45	138	TraverseCityCadillac	0	213	HattiesburgLaurelMS1	0	288	OttumwaAKirksvilleM	.
64	SanDiegoCA1	45	139	TopekaKS1	0	214	GreenvilleSpartanbur	0	289	OttumwaAKirksvilleM	.
65	SiouxFallsMitchellS1	44	140	TerreHautelIN1	0	215	GreenvilleSpartanbur	0	290	NorthPlatteNE1	.
66	MadisonWI1	44	141	TerreHautelIN1	0	216	GreenvilleNewBernWas	0	291	MeridianMS1	.
67	DaytonOH1	44	142	TallahasseeFLThomasv	0	217	GrandRapidsKalamazoo	0	292	MeridianMS1	.
68	ClevelandAkronCanton	44	143	TallahasseeFLThomasv	0	218	GrandJunctionMontros	0	293	MankatoMN1	.
69	AtlantaGA1	44	144	SyracuseNY1	0	219	FtWayneIN1	0	294	JuneauAK1	.
70	RochesterNY1	42	145	SpringfieldMO1	0	220	FtWayneIN1	0	295	HelenaMT1	.
71	MarquetteMI1	42	146	SpringfieldMO1	0	221	FtSmithFayettevilleS	0	296	GreenwoodGreenvilleM	.
72	LosAngelesCA1	39	147	SpokaneWA1	0	222	FtMyersNaplesFL1	0	297	GreatFallsMT1	.
73	JacksonMS1	39	148	SpokaneWA1	0	223	FlorenceMyrtleBeachS	0	298	GlendiveMT1	.
74	HoustonTX1	39	149	SiouxFallsMitchellS1	0	224	FlorenceMyrtleBeachS	0	299	FairbanksAK1	.
75	GreensboroHighPointW	38	150	SiouxCityIA1	0	225	FargoValleyCityND1	0	300	CasperRivertonWY1	.
									301	AlpenaMI1	.

Notes: Search results for naloxone and related queries for 2010m1.
 Source: DM (2022) replication package (Google.MET.dta).

Table 3 shows DM's data for 2010m1, which can be compared to Table 2. For expositional convenience, the observations in the table are sorted by the search index ('IDX') and numbered with a variable 'N.' The data structure is different from what can be expected from Google Trends. There are repeated metropolitan areas as well as search indexes. In Google Trends, repeated values for areas are not feasible, while indices (which are ratios) are extremely unlikely to be equal, particularly in large quantities (although rounding might make them look equal). Zero is also not a value that Google Trends can generate.

Generally, refining Google search results simultaneously in both the time and location dimensions is unattainable. One can obtain either national high-frequency data or, conversely, annual data specific to metropolitan areas. The availability of both high-frequency and spatially granular Google search data is non-existent for unique topics such as naloxone. This completes the investigation into DM's Google search data. The conclusion is that the Google search data fails the recreate reproducibility, and what is included in the DM replication package has an unverifiable origin.

Notes: Combining data across jurisdictions to provide a national-level perspective.
 Source: DM (2022) replication package (Crime_Data.dta).

B. Crime. The crime analysis conducted by DM relies on data from NIBRS spanning 2010-2015. The data are publicly accessible from the United States Bureau of Justice Statistics (2024). Scrutinizing the steps DM took between retrieving the crime data and running their regression is impossible as DM do not include the cleaning codes. A straightforward approach that circumvents the need for understanding DM's data manipulations is aggregating data to the national level, inspecting the trend, and comparing these trends with those reported elsewhere.

Figure 1 presents the results of aggregating data for 'All theft.' This series, sourced directly from NIBRS data (AUCR codes 231 to 238), is the only one not constructed by DM. It is created by data NIBRS custodians, which minimizes potential data management errors in constructing this time series and makes it a natural comparison benchmark for other outcomes in the DM package. All other crime variables apart from 'All theft' used in DM's analysis are crafted by DM and are not readily available in NIBRS. The visual representation of the time series in Figure 1 appears credible. It shows a general downward trend and a strong seasonality.

Figures 2 and 3 display additional crime variables from the replication package, which are not directly available in NIBRS and must be derived from individual incident data. Notably, the count for certain crimes in 2015 is entirely zeros, and there are almost no recorded 'Opioid-related thefts.' Since 'Opioid-related thefts' are part of the broader 'All theft' category, which does not show an instantaneous drop in 2015, these two time series cannot coexist in the same dataset.

Alternatively, we can resort to the Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI) Crime Data Explorer (FBI, 2024), which directly visualizes national and state crime data. It is easy to confirm using the tab 'Arrest' that in 2015, there were about 1 million drug possession arrests, which is inconsistent with zero crimes data in the DM replication package. Finally, Figures 4 and 5 depict, for each state, a fentanyl possession variable constructed by DM. For all states, 2015 shows a zero crime rate. A similar problem is present for other crimes constructed by DM. This concludes the recreate reproducibility, concluding that their crime data does not reproduce.

The overarching concern is whether NIBRS drug crime data was ever suitable for DM's research question, with

Figure 4. DM's fentanyl possession crimes by state, part 1

Notes: Combining data across jurisdictions to provide a state-level perspective. Incident per million is shown.
 Source: DM (2022) replication package (Crime_Data.dta).

Figure 5. DM's fentanyl possession crimes by state, part 2

Notes: Combining data across jurisdictions to provide a state-level perspective. Incident per million is shown.
 Source: DM (2022) replication package (Crime.Data.dta).

existing literature suggesting it might not be. DM presumably uses NIBRS AUCR code 35A for Drug/Narcotic Violations, specifying the drug type, and V20141 to indicate if the violation involves selling or buying. However, criminological literature, as noted by Jarvis (p. 200, 2015), highlights the unreliability of these NIBRS variables, pointing out potential underreporting by up to 60%. This underreporting stems from law enforcement's reluctance to document drug use, fearing it might affect case integrity. Additionally, detailed drug information is not prioritized in violent crime investigations with apparent perpetrators, and drug testing is costly and often unnecessary for effective police work.

It is important to carefully assess the suitability of NIBRS data for specific crime types. For instance, research by Addington (2004) suggests that even murder cases might be inaccurately reported in NIBRS. Similarly, studies focusing on intimate partner violence crimes highlight substantial underreporting of drug use information in the arrest available in NIBRS (Pattavina, Hirschel, and Scarbo 2013). April Pattavina, while revising the current papers, also notes a potential measurement issue related to monthly counts. Although an agency may provide data to the NIBRS program, they may not supply it for all 12 months. This issue is particularly relevant when agencies are new to reporting. A variable in the data indicates how many months of reporting the agency provided data for a particular year. DM package does not include this variable.

The underreporting of drug crimes in NIBRS is distinct from the broader issue of underreported drug crimes in general. In criminology, it is widely recognized that drug crimes often poorly represent overall drug use. These offenses, classified as crimes against society, are characterized by sparse reporting due to the absence of a direct victim. Consequently, reliance on law enforcement initiatives to uncover such offenses means drug crimes are more likely to be accidentally discovered rather than actively reported (Moffatt, Wan, and Weatherburn 2012). This underscores that using police-reported drug crimes may not accurately reflect the true intensity of drug use, suggesting that DM's chosen data may have always been inadequate for their research goals.

According to Addington (2009), NIBRS faces three key challenges: data quality concerns, particularly for certain crimes like drug offenses, and incomplete spatial coverage. These limitations lead criminologists, who prioritize data reliability, to avoid using NIBRS in their research. To the best of my knowledge, no studies have analyzed monthly drug crimes similar to those reported in DM. Furthermore, when comparing DM's drug crimes with data from the FBI Crime Data Explorer, I opted for arrests instead of crimes because the web resource does not report drug crimes. The 'Crime' tab allows the selection and plotting of 10 types of crimes at the national or state level, but drug crimes are notably absent. This absence aligns with the lack of reliable data suitable for research purposes, especially at the monthly level.

It would have also been helpful if DM had provided details on how they constructed the drug crime data, particularly in verifying and reporting the fraction of cases with missing information on drug type. According to the NIBRS documentation, data on drug type may be missing if an incident involves more than three drug types, and clarification on how these cases were handled would improve transparency. Additionally, the NIBRS data seems to lack specific information on fentanyl, yet DM appears to refer to 'Other Narcotics' and fentanyl interchangeably, which would benefit from further explanation.

C. Hospitalization. DM's opioid-related ER visits conclusions are based on HCUP, covering 2006 to 2015. An advantage of HCUP is its easy accessibility and minimal additional data preparations required, which enables a direct comparison of the data from the replication package and the data custodians. The state-quarter data available includes counts of admissions as well as rates per 100,000. Whether counts or rates are used is not explained in DM, but it can be easily deduced by noticing that the HCUP methodology rounds visit counts to the nearest 50, which is what we see in the DM data.

In the data, patient location is based on the five categories: (1) Large central metropolitan — 1 million or more population; (2) Large fringe metropolitan — 1 million or more population; (3) Medium metropolitan — Populations of 250,000 to 999,999; (4) Small metropolitan — population less than 250,000; (5) Rural — the micropolitan (population between 10,000 and 49,99) or noncore categories (less than 10,000 residents). DM sum categories (1) to (4) and discard (5) in their analysis.

Figure 6. DM's and true opioid-related ER visits, part 1

Notes: Full data for ER visits. Hollow red circle is the true data, solid blue circle is the DM replication package data.
 Source: HCUP (2024a) and DM (2022) replication package (HCUP_Data.dta).

Figure 7. DM's and true opioid-related ER visits, part 2

Notes: Full data for ER visits. Hollow red circle is the true data, solid blue circle is the DM replication package data.
 Source: HCUP (2024a) and DM (2022) replication package (HCUP_Data.dta).

Figures 6 and 7 present the complete DM data and data directly downloaded from HCUP. Oregon, Texas, Wyoming, and the District of Columbia are excluded from the DM's dataset. Fifteen states exhibit missing quarters, and ten states have data that deviates from what is independently retrieved (see Georgia for a vivid illustration). Many states most significantly impacted by the opioid epidemic during this time, such as West Virginia, New Hampshire, and Pennsylvania, are absent from the dataset. Despite this, DM refer to these states when discussing the access laws' introduction, and they are included in DM's Table 1 and Figure 3. This potentially misleads readers into assuming their inclusion in the analysis. Consequently, even if the results were internally valid, they are not representative.

Exploring the national trends suggested by the data is insightful. In Figure 8, independently retrieved data from HCUP (2024a) is marked with a hollow circle, while smaller blue circles represent DM's data. The figure shows a significant decline in opioid-related admissions in the United States, with DM's data indicating a drop from 85,000 to 50,000 in Q1 2015. However, when the actual data is used, this decline is not observed. Instead, there is an unprecedented increase beginning in 2015, partially likely due to the transition from ICD-9-CM to ICD-10-CM/PCS on October 1, 2015. HCUP clearly documents this transition in the Excel file containing the data and on a dedicated web resource (HCUP, 2022).

The transition makes the data time series inconsistent. To address this inconsistency, the Centers for Medicare Medicaid Services (CMS) and the National Center for Health Statistics (NCHS) have developed General Equivalence Mappings (GEMs), which provide well-documented and comprehensive tools for converting between ICD-9-CM and ICD-10-CM/PCS codes, enabling researchers to maintain consistency in time series data spanning the transition period. Notably, DM do not attempt to convert or equalize the time series, nor do they mention the ICD transition or any methods to deal with it in their paper.

The quantile plot shown in Figure 9 reveals an unusual feature: a notable gap in values between 11,000 and 12,000, which diverges from the expected quantile distribution. This gap is also evident in the original data, highlighting an issue that may require clarification from the data custodians. Ideally, researchers working with such data, including DM, would examine and report on such anomalies to enhance the transparency and reliability of the analysis.

The conclusion regarding the recreation of reproducibility is clear, and the replication exercise is complete. The hospitalization data cannot be reproduced. The data that supported the DM conclusions is not viable for making valid conclusions. While the conclusion on the DM hospitalization data is clear, it is worth discussing HCUP data more for future researchers. For instance, the absence of information for some states in 2014 and 2015 suggests that DM downloaded data in mid-2016, and some states submitted data later. A pertinent question arises regarding the prevalence of missing data in other studies that utilize HCUP. If some states submit data later, it renders data missingness not at random, a point further discussed in Section 4. Of note is that HCUP is widely recognized as a validated and trusted data source, and there is no information about the differential timing of submission by states in HCUP documentation (Houchens et al. 2014).

Notes: The top figure aggregates state-level data to the national level, while the bottom plots quantiles for the original state-quarter data.
Source: HCUP (2024a) and DM (2022) replication package (HCUP.Data.dta).

4. Design & implementation

A. Timing. The treatment parameter in the DD design relies on accurately distinguishing between treated and untreated groups before and after the intervention, making the risks associated with misclassifying the timing of naloxone-related measures highly relevant. The safest approach involves categorizing states that initiated some form of naloxone access law — the first enactments — as the treatment timing. This ensures a well-defined control group comprising states with no broadening of naloxone access whatsoever.

However, accurately determining the timing of naloxone access laws presents challenges due to the complex and state-specific nature of these regulations. The legal landscape surrounding naloxone access is characterized by intricate state-level variations and frequent modifications, leading to considerable ambiguity in interpretation. This complexity has spurred substantial scholarly efforts to accurately classify and characterize these laws in all their nuances.

In response to these challenges, the research community has created multiple publicly available resources to aid in the accurate classification of naloxone access laws. Notable among these are the Network for Public Health Law (NPHL, 2023) and the Prescription Drug Abuse Policy System (PDAPS, 2022). These resources provide detailed chronologies of naloxone access law enactments and subsequent modifications, referencing the underlying state statutory laws.

Given this context, the approach taken by DM in their study raises concerns. DM claim to have ‘hand-collected information about the timing of naloxone access laws in each state’ but provide limited details on their methodology. The absence of a dedicated methods section that outlines the specific legal criteria for naloxone access laws is particularly troubling. As noted by Corey Davis in his review of this replication, this omission is akin to omitting the methods section in an applied econometrics paper. Davis has not only systematically categorized naloxone access laws using historical legal databases but was also instrumental in developing the chronologically detailed NPHL naloxone enactments list (Davis and Carr 2015).

From an econometric perspective, the lack of clear legal criteria poses challenges for identification. Even if the identifying assumptions were correct, the absence of a well-defined legal framework undermines the unique mapping between the data and the parameter of interest, thereby compromising the validity of the findings.

Table 4 summarizes the dates of the first naloxone law enactments as reported by NPHL and those listed in DM’s Table 1, including only the dates that substantially differ. The discrepancies are striking and widespread, highlighting the unreliability of DM’s hand-collected data.

Interestingly, DM’s treatment of North Carolina stands out as an exception to this pattern of inconsistency. In their Section 3, DM provide a detailed account of naloxone distribution in North Carolina following the law’s enactment, accurately reflecting the legal timeline as reported by NPHL. This suggests that the authors may have implicitly defined a legal criterion similar to that of NPHL for this particular case study. However, this level of scrutiny and accuracy is not applied consistently across other states.

Table 4. Disagreement on timing of the naloxone laws

State	DM Table 1	NPHL Dates
Colorado	April 1, 2015	May 10, 2013
Connecticut	June 1, 2015	October 1, 2003
Illinois	September 1, 2015	January 1, 2010
Kentucky	March 1, 2015	June 25, 2013
Louisiana	June 1, 2016	August 1, 2015
Maine	October 1, 2015	April 29, 2014
Maryland	October 1, 2015	October 1, 2013
New York	June 1, 2014	April 1, 2006
Rhode Island	October 1, 2014	June 18, 2012
Virginia	April 1, 2015	July 1, 2013
Washington	July 1, 2015	June 10, 2010
California	January 1, 2014	January 1, 2008

Notes: Comparison of DM naloxone law timing and those retrieved independently.

Source: DM (2022) replication package and NPHL (2023).

B. Exogeneity. A canonical assumption in the DD design is the ‘no anticipation’ assumption. This assumption stipulates that a state’s outcome does not depend on its future treatments (Chaisemartin and D’Haultfoeulle 2023). Failure of this assumption invalidates DD results even if the ‘common trends’ assumption holds. However, in the context of naloxone access laws, this assumption is likely violated. This issue of treatment endogeneity is well-documented in the economics literature, particularly in studies of minimum wage laws, where researchers have long recognized that the timing of policy changes often correlates with economic conditions (p. 292, MacKinnon, Nielsen, and Webb 2022).

States are more likely to introduce naloxone access laws in response to high levels of all three collections of outcomes analyzed: crime, hospitalization, or public interest. Opioid-related admissions and theft are explicitly mentioned as motivations for the laws themselves. This is evident in the legislative text (e.g., New York State Senate 2021) and can be verified through media searches (e.g., Rapaport 2017). Moreover, when considering the public interest, how can Google searches accurately reflect an interest in naloxone or drug rehabilitation by drug users if society at large was already discussing naloxone extensively around the time of its introduction? There were also educational campaigns that directly increased awareness of naloxone.

DM's Section 3 highlights another logical inconsistency in their use of Google searches: the distribution of naloxone kits by institutions such as the North Carolina Harm Reduction Coalition. This example, which they document in detail, underscores that institutions purchase these kits rather than individual users. Therefore, widespread interest in naloxone is not demonstrated by individual searches but by state-level institutions. Considering that each state typically has only one or two such institutions, the level of public interest captured by Google searches would be minimal and unable to reflect the broader interest accurately. Consequently, relying on Google searches as a measure of public interest in naloxone for this reason only appears flawed, given that the searches primarily represent institutional actions rather than widespread individual interest.

While assessing pre-trends can provide some support for the plausibility of the common trend assumption in a DD analysis, it should be complemented with logical reasoning. Logical reasoning, as emphasized by many others, is crucial in judging the validity of a DD design (Rambachan and Roth 2023; Jaeger, Joyce, and Kaestner 2020; Roth 2022). Unfortunately, assessing pre-trends appears to be the only measure DM present to support the validity of their results.

DM do not perform statistical tests to verify whether treatment effects before the law are jointly equal to zero, a practice often used to assess the plausibility of pre-trends in support of the common trend assumption. Instead, they visually inspect the common trend by displaying only four quarters before the law and three quarters after while estimating leads and lags beyond those quarters using the remaining quarters.

Table 5 illustrates this using their HCUP data for Massachusetts, where the quarter -5 estimate (as indicated in the column 'dd0' in the table) is based on 23 quarters (2006q1 to 2011q3). This approach is overly restrictive and largely assumes the common trend rather than verifying it with the data. As demonstrated by my independent DD estimates in Section 5, specifying a more flexible model reveals a significant bias in trends that becomes apparent two years prior to the law's enactment. Importantly, nowhere in their work do they explain that this is the approach they take. In addition, and as a minor point, DM do not describe anywhere whether the event plots in DM's Figure 5 show confidence intervals or standard errors.

C. Missing data. DM expand the study period for hospitalization outcomes to 2006-2015 while only using 2010-2015 for crime and internet searchers analysis. They argue this extension enhances statistical power. However, it is crucial to note that between 2006 and 2009, only one state enacted naloxone laws according to the DM's choice of legal criteria: New Mexico. Ironically, New Mexico is entirely absent from their dataset. Interestingly, as illustrated in Table 4 and pointed out by Corey Davis, New York enacted its naloxone law in 2006 and is present in the dataset; DM, however, coded this state as control up until 2014.*

The precision of the treatment parameter in DD hinges on the means for treated and untreated groups before and

*. For completeness, for the period starting in 2006, the current advice would be to exclude New York since it is an always-treated state without comparisons (Sant'Anna 2023).

Table 5. Testing for the common trend with distribute lag model

ST	qt	HN	dd0	dd1	dd2	dd3	dd4	dd5	dd6	dd7	dd8
MA	2006q1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
MA	2011q3	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MA	2011q4	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MA	2012q1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
MA	2012q2	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
MA	2012q3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
MA	2012q4	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
MA	2013q1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
MA	2013q2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
MA	2013q3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
MA	2014q4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1

Notes: dd0 is -5 quarter, dd1 is -4 and so on. HN is the treatment dummy.
Source: DM (2022) replication package (HCUP_Data.dta).

after the intervention. States appearing solely in the pre- or post-period do not contribute to estimating the treatment effect, as the group-period interaction term remains constant for such states. Thus, from a basic mechanics of DD, it is impossible to improve the precision of the DD treatment effect by including observation only for untreated units. The change in estimates that DM experienced is not an increased power but a bias driven by data missing not at random exacerbated by the DM control variable vector.

The potential for bias depends on the nature of data absence — if quarters are missing based on intervention or outcome, the treatment effect may be significantly biased. It is conceivable that the missing hospitalization data is non-random, given that decisions regarding the management and sharing of such data are likely made by the same bureaucrats responsible for shaping overall health policy. These bureaucrats' choices could reflect a correlation between the quality of health policy and the decision to opt out of data collection, potentially indicating a predisposition to enact naloxone laws.

The decision to include past years exacerbates the bias driven by the data missing nonrandomly, particularly because of the 9 variables that DM included in their regression to control for other state-specific laws affecting hospitalization, such as tamper-resistant prescription forms. The data is likely missing depending on at least some of these laws. Thus, the inclusion of the control variable vector exacerbates the bias driven by data missing not randomly, with the bias more likely to have a stronger effect the longer the panel (Zhao, Ding, and Li 2024).

The 9 control variables used also have an unclear origin and questionable validity. In footnote 18, DM mention using a database from Meara et al. (2016) to construct control variables for state-level drug policies. However, the referenced paper lacks specific information on policy timings. Although it offers overviews of existing policies in the supplementary appendix, it only provides cumulative data on enacted policies without detailing the timing for each policy at the state level.

During a revision of the current replication, the authors provided additional information about the data source. They indicated that at the time of their publication, the dataset was available on a website associated with the Dartmouth Atlas of Health Care. However, this website and the specific file are not mentioned anywhere in the original DM paper and are currently not available online. The Wayback Machine — Internet Archive also cannot verify the existence of these files between 2018 and 2022.[†] They also mentioned that these dates could potentially be obtained by contacting Ellen Meara. I reached out to the professor on January 20, 2024, but as of this version, I have not received a response.

If DM aimed to increase the number of quarter-state observations, a straightforward approach would have been to avoid aggregating metropolitan areas and instead maintain data by metropolitan type. This alternative method could have resulted in a larger sample size and a better balance between treated and untreated units before and after the law's implementation. If necessary, they could have further interacted the treatment dummy with metropolitan type to examine potential differences in effects across these categories.

As noted by Corey Davis, a simpler way to enhance statistical power, which would also align with research integrity, would have been to update the data prior to publication. The work was published in 2022, but the earliest complete working paper had been available on the Social Science Research Network since 2018. This gap presented an opportunity to incorporate more recent data. Interestingly, as this replication study reveals, such an update might have led to different conclusions, potentially tempering the more provocative aspects of DM.

D. Implementation. Table 6 provides descriptive statistics for the DM dataset. However, upon comparison with DM's Table 2, where similar statistics are reported, discrepancies for all crime measures emerge. For example, the reported mean for 'All theft' data in DM is 1727, with a standard deviation of 961. These values deviate noticeably from those presented in Table 6. DM potentially report the crime count as opposed to the rate, but the table note clearly states the rate.

Table 6 provides additional information about the DM data, illustrating the econometric challenges that their implementation of the DD design faces. The last column shows that the outcomes are skewed, with some having zeros

[†]. The website mentioned during the review is <https://www.dartmouthatlas.org/>. Specifically, they referred to a file named 'Opioids and state laws.xlsx.' The Wayback Machine — Internet Archive address that can be reviewed is available at https://web.archive.org/web/20200527040005/https://atlasdata.dartmouth.edu/static/supp_research_data.

Table 6. Descriptive statistics

Variable	G	N	Mean	SD	Min	p1	p5	p10	p25	p50	p75	p90	p95	p99	Max	Skew
Opioids possessions	30	29808	3.126	5.349	0	0	0	0	0	1	4	8	13	27	76	3.770
Opioids selling	30	29808	0.872	2.212	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	4	11	38	5.378
Fentanyl possessions	30	29808	1.142	2.260	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	5	10	45	4.900
Fentanyl selling	30	29808	0.251	0.864	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	4	17	6.464
Opioid-related crime	30	29808	5.055	8.218	0	0	0	0	1	2	6	13	21	42	117	3.601
Opioid-related theft	30	29808	0.199	0.566	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	3	9	4.207
All theft	30	29808	183.180	274.045	0	8	21	30	54	98	193	385	605	1550	3112	4.353
Opioid-related ER visits	32	1108	1938.132	2360.283	0	50	50	100	375	1100	2575	4750	6650	12500	15650	2.422
Google search naloxone	48	20232	27.979	25.192	0	0	0	0	0	26	43	62	77	100	100	0.760
Google search drug rehab	48	21528	50.254	19.954	0	0	16	23	37	52	63	74	82	100	100	-0.093

Notes: 'G' is the number of clusters.
 Source: DM (2022) replication package (all dta files).

for most of the data, as shown by the values at various quantiles. Interestingly, the skewness goes in the opposite direction for two Google search data. These skews suggest that linear models might inadequately represent marginal effects across the entire distribution due to the lack of a non-negative restriction on the conditional mean function if it is estimated with an OLS estimator (Ch. 18, Wooldridge 2010). The Poisson pseudo-maximum likelihood (PPML) estimator presents a well-understood alternative to OLS for DD (Correia, Guimarães, and Zylkin 2020; Wooldridge 2023).

Another challenge is the number of clusters reported in the column 'G.' The crime data, as reported in DM, cover 33 states, yet their model only utilizes 30 states due to the inclusion of additional control variables. Table 6 correctly shows only the number of clusters for the non-missing data used in the regressions. As for hospitalization data, the number of states is completely undiscussed in DM. Table 6 shows that there are 32 states for 'Opioid-related ER visits,' which is low enough to warrant a more detailed discussion. A variance estimator with better finite sample properties is needed with such a limited number of clusters (MacKinnon, Nielsen, and Webb 2022).

DM employ a conventional CV1 estimator, which may oversimplify uncertainty and increase type I error. CV1's asymptotics require infinite, equally sized clusters, a condition not met by crime and hospitalization data. For Google search outcomes, although the number of clusters is larger, they are highly unequal, verifiable with the Stata package `summcust` (MacKinnon, Nielsen, and Webb 2023). Table 7 presents `summcust` results, highlighting substantial cluster heterogeneity and cautioning against CV1 use. Notably, the 'max' row in the 'Partial L.' column shows that one cluster contributes 43% to the treatment effect, and effective cluster analysis reveals only 8 clusters when accounting for this heterogeneity. The `summcust` authors emphasize monitoring the scaled variance of partial leverages, suggesting CV1 becomes unreliable above 0.27. In Table 7, this value, found at the bottom of the 'Partial L.' column in the 'coefvar' row, is 3.0191, necessitating alternative variance estimation methods.

Table 8 presents results when DM models are reestimated using a correct conditional mean function and an appropriate variance estimator. As a reminder, the reestimation is performed using the DD design, which has endogenous and incorrect law timing on data that failed the recreate reproducibility. For both OLS and PPML estimators, average marginal effects are reported; therefore, the point estimates can be directly compared. The OLS estimates with CV1, presented in the leftmost column, correspond to what is reported in DM. The only distinction is that the analytic weights for the crime outcome are not applied because, for PPML or CV3, these weights are meaningless (e.g., Santos Silva and Tenreiro 2022) and not permitted by Stata. The alternative variance estimator used is CV3, as existing and emerging literature indicates that this estimator fits settings with a reduced number or unbalanced clusters well (Mancl and DeRouen 2004; Hansen 2022; MacKinnon, Nielsen, and Webb 2024).

The OLS estimates with appropriately evaluated standard errors clearly illustrate the fragility of DM's findings. For all outcomes, the correct accounting for data uncertainty results in a substantial loss of efficiency and statistical confidence. The only two outcomes that remain significant at the 5% level are 'Opioid-related theft' and 'Google search

Table 7. Cluster influence for search on naloxone

Cluster variability				
Statistic	Ng	Leverage	Partial L.	beta no g
min	72.0	2.259	0.000	1.536
q1	216.0	6.791	0.003	1.753
median	432.0	13.610	0.006	1.861
mean	421.5	13.375	0.021	1.844
q3	576.0	18.104	0.011	1.941
max	1296.0	41.070	0.428	2.141
coefvar	0.620	0.621	3.019	0.069
Effective number of clusters				
ρ	0	0.5	1	
$G^*(\rho)$	25.275	25.275	8.457	

Notes: Stata package `summcust` applied to the DM regression for Google search naloxone.
 Source: DM (2022) replication package (Google_MET.dta).

Table 8. Alternative design implementation

	OLS					PPML				
	Estimate	CV1		CV3		Estimate	CV1		CV3	
		SE	P value	SE	P value		SE	P value	SE	P value
Opioids possessions	4.134	2.134	0.063	2.819	0.153	2.423	1.620	0.135	2.128	0.255
Opioids selling	1.986	0.830	0.023	1.063	0.072	1.686	0.711	0.018	0.818	0.039
Fentanyl possessions	2.188	1.117	0.060	1.499	0.155	0.096	0.969	0.921	1.212	0.937
Fentanyl selling	0.864	0.525	0.110	0.590	0.153	1.179	0.490	0.016	0.632	0.062
Opioid-related crime	6.082	2.917	0.046	3.951	0.135	3.749	1.958	0.055	2.511	0.135
Opioid-related theft	0.432	0.170	0.017	0.208	0.047	0.132	0.143	0.358	0.166	0.427
All theft	11.239	13.812	0.422	14.853	0.455	-0.691	17.095	0.968	19.494	0.972
Opioid-related ER visits	265.909	121.691	0.037	137.167	0.062	1.770	54.325	0.974	67.664	0.979
Google search naloxone	1.847	0.813	0.028	0.865	0.038	1.114	0.584	0.056	0.628	0.076
Google search drug rehab	-0.799	0.453	0.084	0.497	0.114	-0.962	0.451	0.033	0.498	0.054

Notes: Reestimating DM models with alternative estimators.

Source: DM (2022) replication package (all dta files).

naloxone.’ Other results previously significant at 5% become significant only at 10%. This change in ‘P value’ implies that modest evidence becomes only a suggestion of evidence (Ch. 8.4.3, Cox and Donnelly 2011). The rightmost column reports the results when both the conditional mean and variance estimator are appropriate. Only one result, ‘Opioids selling’, is significant at 5%.

The substantial differences in point estimates across estimators for most outcomes indicate that many zeros affect the marginal effect, rendering OLS regression potentially unreliable. For ‘Opioid-related ER visits,’ the difference is particularly extreme. OLS estimates the treatment effect as an increase of 266 admissions, whereas Poisson estimates only 2 admissions. The PPML applies a log transformation to the outcome (thus, the estimator is more robust to outliers than OLS), and the difference in point estimates suggests the presence of outliers.

To investigate these outliers, Figure 10 presents a leverage versus normalized squared residuals (L-R) plot following the OLS estimator. This plot displays leverage on the vertical axis and normalized squared residuals on the horizontal axis. The vertical red line marks the average normalized squared residuals, with observations to the right having above-average residuals. The horizontal red line marks the average leverage, with observations above it having above-average leverage. High leverage points, which lack close neighboring observations, can skew the OLS regression line. Observations with large squared residuals indicate significant deviations from the predicted values, suggesting outliers. It can be shown that outliers are from the post-treatment period, suggesting that the treatment effect has a dynamic component. Using the terminology of Chaisemartin and D’Haultfoeulle (2023), the ‘no dynamic effect’ assumption is violated, rendering the conventional discrete DD results less meaningful. Section 5 offers estimates based on a more appropriate dynamic model.

Notes: Leverage vs squared residuals plot.
Source: DM (2022) replication package (HCUP_Data.dta).

E. Miscellany. HCUP data includes both hospitalization rates and counts. It is unclear why DM prefer the count data over rates, especially since they normalize crime data by population and use analytical weights. For hospitalization data, their regression model lacks population information. While this is not problematic due to the population being constant conditionally on state- and time-fixed effects, it is peculiar that they use different modeling approaches for two similar regressands. Importantly, the use of count data is not reported in the paper, requiring an examination of the replication package to determine what was actually used. During the review of this replication, the authors explained that count was likely selected because other papers did the same, but no specific papers were cited to justify this decision in either the revision or original publication.

According to DM, their OLS estimate of 266 ER admissions corresponds to a 15% increase. Their paper shows that this 15% increase is statistically significant with a P value less than 0.05. However, the paper does not explain how they arrived at this percent change and how statistical significance was established. Arguably not using a PPML

estimator, as it shows no effect. Alternatively, Stata supports numerical derivatives after OLS with errors based on delta methods, enabling the estimation of semi-elasticities as if the outcome is in logarithmic terms (Baum 2010; Boggess and MacDonald 2013). A numerical derivative correctly employs the estimated conditional mean function to estimate the semi-elasticity, which aligns with the recommendation provided by Wooldridge (1992). The resulting output indicates a 46.73% increase, which is not statistically significant ($P = 0.967$, 95% CI from -22 to 22). This massive relative increase and the statistical insignificance align with the presence of outliers and no effect when PPML is used.

A few additional notes. DM includes police per capita as a control when analyzing Google searches and crime but omits this for hospitalization outcomes without explanation. Further, Michael Wiebe pointed out during his review of this replication that Google Trends data, based on random search samples, requires robustness checks to confirm findings are not sample-specific. Data also needs to be downloaded in one day; collecting across multiple days disrupts sample integrity, as each day might yield a different sample, challenging the assumption of a consistent, nationally representative dataset, particularly when applied to monthly metropolitan area analyses. This is exacerbated by DM's practice of replacing missing Google Trends data with zeros, which is statistically flawed as it equates no searches with missing data due to privacy thresholds, potentially skewing results. If zeros replaced missing values, the researchers should have used censoring regression to correct for this substitution.

Another comment is on the inference for the Google search regressions. Table 3 establishes that DM's Google search data for naloxone has repeated values. DM could have used Stata's package `reghdfe` (Correia 2023) to include state fixed effects. They opted for Stata's native `xtreg`, which does not permit repeated panel IDs for the same period. Table 9 demonstrates how they managed to run `xtreg`.

The table shows 301 metropolitan areas in the variable 'MET' and a variable indicating a state 'ST'. The variable 'mt' concatenates these two and adds an underscore between them. This variable is the panel identifier DM use for enabling `xtreg` with `xtset`. There are problems with this approach. For example, there are only 210 areas in Google Trends, as seen in Table 2, but the unverifiable origin of data or lack of economic sense is already discussed. Here, I call for attention to, for example, observations 7-9 in Table 9, which is Amarillo, Texas. Observation number 9, with the value 'TX' of the variable 'ST', is correct; however, observations 7 and 8 have values 'OK' and 'NM.' This is meaningless, as there is neither an Amarillo, Texas in Oklahoma nor New Mexico. All repeated metropolitan areas have incorrect state identifiers added to them to appear different. This approach makes the inference statistically invalid, as it violates the assumption of independence across units selected to be independent. Neither the CV1 nor CV3 variance estimators work properly here; by misclassifying observations in Texas as being in Oklahoma or New Mexico, the analysis incorrectly assumes that these observations are uncorrelated with other observations in Texas.

During the review of my replication, DM defended their approach of creating repeated metropolitan areas with the same value under different state labels, arguing that people may commute across states for work, shopping, or entertainment. However, this worsens the issue as the mentioned spillovers lead to biased estimates, not only in standard errors but also in the regression function parameters, as treatment externalities indicate a violation of the Stable Unit Treatment Value Assumption.

5. Alternative estimates

DM note on page 222 that 'Violence is not generally an expected outcome of opioid abuse.' This unique association between opioids and violence is well-supported in criminology and addiction literature, as reviewed, for example,

Table 9. DM's area identifiers for Google searches

N	MET	ST	mt
1	AbileneSweetwaterTX1	TX	TX_AbileneSweetwaterTX1
2	AlbanyGA1	GA	GA_AlbanyGA1
3	AlbanySchenectadyTro	NY	NY_AlbanySchenectadyTro
4	AlbuquerqueSantaFeN1	NM	NM_AlbuquerqueSantaFeN1
5	AlexandriaLA1	LA	LA_AlexandriaLA1
6	AlpenaMI1	MI	MI_AlpenaMI1
7	AmarilloTX1	OK	OK_AmarilloTX1
8	AmarilloTX1	NM	NM_AmarilloTX1
9	AmarilloTX1	TX	TX_AmarilloTX1
:	:	:	:
297	YoungstownOH1	PA	PA_YoungstownOH1
298	YoungstownOH1	OH	OH_YoungstownOH1
299	YumaAZEICentroCA1	CA	CA_YumaAZEICentroCA1
300	YumaAZEICentroCA1	AZ	AZ_YumaAZEICentroCA1
301	ZanesvilleOH1	OH	OH_ZanesvilleOH1

Notes: Column mt is the panel ID.
Source: DM (2022) replication package (Google.MET.dta).

by Alexeev and Weatherburn (2025). Injurious events have a looser association with heroin use because opioids, as opposed to alcohol or stimulants, have an acute depressive impact on the nervous system. This suggests that injuries, which are often driven by alcohol or stimulants but rarely by opioids, could serve as an additional contrast within a triple difference (TD) design.

The TD design will reduce potential treatment endogeneity issues, as the design now requires there be no contemporaneous shock that affects the relative outcomes between ER groups in the same state-quarter cell as the law. TD is also much better at isolating potential treatment spillovers through the interacted fixed effects. For example, the transition from ICD-9-CM to ICD-10-CM/PCS on October 1, 2015, makes the time series inconsistent (HCUP, 2022). However, including two types of ER admissions, which are both affected, will guard against data inconsistency better. TD also improves inference by explicitly modeling data clustering with exhaustive fixed effects and indirectly via the clustered variance estimator (Olden and Møen 2022).

As argued in the previous section, out of three datasets included in the DM replication package, ER admissions are the only viable and easily independently accessible data source. Restricted-use LMFs, which is also used by DM but not available in the replication package, would also work, but accessing data by non-US researchers is particularly difficult. I augment the opioid admission dataset by including injury-related ER admissions by adults, using another source available at HCUP (2024b). In contrast to DM, however, I do not exclude rural areas.

Figure 13 displays national trends for the data, with the vertical black line marking 2018q4, the data points beyond which data is excluded from the analysis. The most recent values are excluded because both types of ER admissions are significantly lower than what previous trends would suggest. Notably, opioid ER admissions have remained at zero in the last three quarters, which is clinically implausible. The DM data shows similar patterns in Figure 8, where the last quarters go down. This finding is crucial as it raises questions about the extensive literature relying on HCUP data. Studies that do not explicitly discuss that up to five years of data potentially suffer severe missingness may lack internal validity.

Notes: Aggregating state-level data.
Source: Opioid (HCUP, 2024a) and injuries (HCUP, 2024b) ER visits.

Figures 11 and 12 show the complete data with the black solid vertical line showing which of the most recent quarters are excluded. The thicker, dashed red line shows the dates of the law's first enactment as provided in NPHL (2023). The data is not ideal for a DD design. For example, Alaska enacted the law in 2016q1, but the data series for opioid-related ER visits only starts in 2019q1. Thus, the treatment dummy for this state does not switch, meaning the state has no comparison period. Similar issues exist in Connecticut, Michigan, the District of Columbia, Colorado, and Oregon. One way to deal with states that are always treated is to exclude them or move the data's beginning to the right. However, the TD framework may offer a better solution as it uses additional comparisons across ER visit types. In practice, the estimates I report are nearly identical whether the always treated states are excluded or not; therefore, I have chosen to keep them in the data for the reported event plots.

Notably, 7 out of 40 states show an increase in admissions following the law. These states include Indiana, Iowa, Maine, North Dakota, Utah, South Carolina, and Nebraska. They are known to be Republican-leaning, rural, conservative, predominantly white, and have low population densities. This tempts provocative thoughts on the heterogeneity in the effects of naloxone on drug use. However, five other states sharing similar characteristics show no increase: Montana, Wyoming, Kansas, South Dakota, and Vermont. Some states apparently introduced the naloxone access laws coincidentally with the ICD transition, illustrating that the transitioning without proper care may be misinterpreted as an increase in opioid admissions and deaths, including if the CDC data for deaths from the

Figure 11. State-level injuries and opioid ER admissions, part 1

Notes: Full data for injury-related (solid blue circle; left axis) and opioid (hollow red circle; right axis) ER visits. The black vertical line shows excluded data; the red dashed line shows the law onset.

Source: Opioid (HCUP, 2024a) and injuries (HCUP, 2024b) ER visits; Law timing from NPHL (2023).

Figure 12. State-level injuries and opioid ER admissions, part 2

Notes: Full data for injury-related (solid blue circle; left axis) and opioid (hollow red circle; right axis) ER visits. The black vertical line shows excluded data; the red dashed line shows the law onset.

Source: Opioid (HCUP, 2024a) and injuries (HCUP, 2024b) ER visits; Law timing from NPHL (2023).

Figure 14. TD OLS

Notes: $Y_{its} = \delta_{st} + \gamma_{it} + \nu_{is} + \beta_{\tau} D_{its}^{\times}$, where i admission type, s state, t quarter, τ half year, β_{τ} is shown, CI is based on state-clustered CV3. Source: Opioid (HCUP, 2024a) and injuries (HCUP, 2024b) ER visits; Law timing from NPHL (2023).

Figure 15. DD OLS

Notes: $Y_{ts} = \delta_s + \gamma_t + \delta_s T + \beta_{\tau} D_{ts}^{\times}$, where s state, t quarter, τ half year, T is trend, β_{τ} is shown, CI is based on state-clustered CV3. Source: Opioid (HCUP, 2024a) and injuries (HCUP, 2024b) ER visits; Law timing from NPHL (2023).

LMFs is used. The extent to which existing studies are affected by this transition is unclear, as no papers, it seems, have carefully discussed this issue.

Figure 14 shows the estimates where a TD design under constant treatment effects is implemented using a linear three-way interacted fixed effect model, estimated with OLS. The dynamic specification is used instead of a conventional discrete one to account for potential violations of the ‘no dynamic effect’ assumption. Quarters are aggregated to half-years in the treatment interaction to permit estimation. No additional controls are included. The outcome variable is a count of admissions, not the rate. The model satisfies the common trend assumption remarkably well, with a flat trend for 11 years prior to the law.

To complete the discussion, Figure 15 shows a DD design implemented using a linear two-way fixed effect regression with state-trend, estimated with OLS. There is a pretrend with an upward bias. Figure 15 can be compared with DM’s Figure 5c, which shows an event plot for opioid admissions. My plot shows an upward pretrend with a flat dynamic up until four years after the law is enacted, after which the estimates turn negative. Their plot is effectively a rescaled mirror image of mine if the estimates are flipped horizontally.

To clarify why the common trend assumption works well within a TD design: Olden and Møen (2022) demonstrate that a TD design can satisfy the common trend assumption even if the subsumed DDs do not, as long as the biases in the DDs are in the same direction. The strong common trend observed in TD OLS suggests that the DD OLS, which uses variations across ER types, also exhibits an upward pretrend, compensating for the upward pre-treatment trend across states.

6. Concluding remarks

This work investigates DM’s replication package, concluding that certain segments of the data have unclear origins or may contain inconsistencies, raising doubts about DM’s conclusions regarding the moral hazard of using naloxone. While these data issues are substantial, even if these concerns were set aside, the appropriately specified regression model, when applied to the same data using the same methodology, does not substantiate their findings. A closer examination of the assumptions underpinning their identification method uncovers additional conceptual flaws in their empirical design.

On a more substantive note, this study reveals a limitation in our current understanding of the effects of naloxone on drug use. The reliance on Google search data and the challenges associated with crime data suggest that these sources may be unsuitable for investigating this issue. Instead, it suggests that ER admission and mortality data may be the more viable and valuable avenue for exploring the potential impact of naloxone on harm reduction in the context of drug use. However, using ER admissions requires utmost care on the availability of the latest quarters, where data appears to be reported by states selectively. Additionally, the transition from ICD-9 to ICD-10 in 2015-2016 presents another significant challenge, affecting both mortality data and ER admissions. These

challenges collectively prompt a reevaluation of the available data sources and emphasize the importance of employing appropriate metrics and methodologies in advancing our comprehension of critical public health interventions.

I have provided my estimates of the effect of the naloxone laws on ER opioid admissions, correcting the issues on the law dates and data management. I used injuries-related ER admissions within a TD framework to improve the plausibility of the identifying assumptions. The OLS estimates show a remarkably strong satisfaction of the common trend assumption within the proposal design. The conclusion is that naloxone laws neither increased nor decreased opioid ER admissions. The estimated zero is precise for up to 6 years after the law onset. These findings contradict DM's findings and do not support the notion of moral hazard associated with naloxone use.

In conclusion, this study not only underscores the need for better data and stronger identification strategies to fully understand the impact of naloxone on opioid-related outcomes but also emphasizes the importance of careful and transparent research in this sensitive area. The widespread promotion of DM's controversial findings in media outlets and think tanks, despite methodological issues, illustrates how research can significantly influence public perception and policy decisions. My replication effort serves as a cautionary note, reminding us that studies with significant implications for public health and drug policy must be conducted and shared with the utmost rigor and care.

More rigorous studies are required to accurately assess the potential of naloxone and other harm reduction interventions in addressing the opioid crisis. Such research should employ robust methodologies and ensure clarity and precision in interpreting and presenting findings. This is especially important in studies that affect vulnerable populations and shape public attitudes toward drug users and harm reduction strategies.

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Dedication. To all saved by naloxone: your renewed lives are a beacon of hope for families torn apart by addiction's grasp. In your survival, children find solace, and parents find the courage to persevere. To the saved and the saviors, in every breath reclaimed, we see the strength of community and the boundless power of compassion. May your stories echo through time, reminding us that every life is a gift.

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Data Availability Statement. The data and statistical scripts (Stata do-files) that support the findings of this study are openly available in [the WEAI Data and Code Repository at OpenICPSR](#), ensuring full reproducibility of the results.

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